

Discovery of Novel Benzimidazole Hybrids: Molecular Docking and Anticancer Evaluation

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Abstract:

The present study focuses on the design, synthesis, and anticancer evaluation of novel aniline-substituted benzimidazole derivatives. A 2D-QSAR analysis was carried out on 30 known benzimidazole analogues using multiple linear regression (MLR) to identify key structural features influencing anticancer activity. The resulting predictive QSAR model was used to estimate the pIC₅₀ values of newly designed compounds. Computer-aided drug design (CADD) techniques helped select the most promising analogues based on Lipinski's rule of five, drug-likeness, docking scores, and predicted toxicity. Selected compounds were synthesized and confirmed using melting point, R_f values, IR, NMR, and Mass spectral analysis. Their in vitro anticancer activity was evaluated against the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line by MTT assay. Among the synthesized derivatives, compound 2AD exhibited the best cytotoxic activity with an IC₅₀ of 132.80 µg, comparable to the standard drug. Overall, the study identifies promising benzimidazole derivatives with significant anticancer potential and provides a strong foundation for future optimization and drug development.

Key Words: benzimidazole, Computer-aided drug design, anticancer, MTT assay

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer is undoubtedly a major challenge of the modern era and is the second leading cause of death in the world. Cancer is the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells in the body. Cancer grows out of normal cells in the body. Docking is frequently used to predict the binding orientation of small molecule drug candidates to their protein targets in order to predict the affinity and activity of the small molecule. Molecular docking is the process that involves placing molecules in appropriate configurations to interact with a receptor.

2D-QSAR MODEL

The structure of the compounds was built with ACD/Chemsketch Freeware and saved in .mol file format. The molecular descriptors for the studied compound were calculated using Padel-descriptor 2.21 software. Totally 797 descriptors including 2D and 3D properties can be calculated using Padel descriptor. Various descriptors like Autocorrelation, AlogP, atom count electrotopological state descriptors, Crippen MR and logP, extended topological atom count of chemical substructures identified by Laggner, and binary fingerprints.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

This work focused on the development of novel aniline substituted benzimidazole derivatives as anticancer agents for breast carcinoma.

The objectives for the work are To generate a 2D QSAR model of known anticancer benzimidazole derivatives using the software QSAR-INS.To design novel aniline substituted benzimidazole derivatives

and to conduct ADME analysis, Druglikeness studies and Toxicity prediction using softwares like SWISSADME, Pre ADMET, Protox-II etc.To predict the affinity and activity of the analogues to the selected protein target of interest in terms of score through docking using AutoDock Vinawith 2 SRC (thyrosine kinase enzyme).To synthesize a series of novel aniline substituted benzimidazole by conventional method.To characterize the synthesized compounds by various analytical methods viz,

- Determination of Melting point,
- Determination of R_f value by thin layer chromatography(TLC),
- FTIR spectroscopy,
- NMR spectroscopy (¹H and ¹³C NMR)
- Mass spectroscopy.

- To evaluate the anticancer activity of the synthesized compound by MTT assay on breast cancer cell line (MCF7)

MATERIALS

All the chemicals and reagents used in this work were of analytical or synthetic grade. Compounds procured were purified and dried using standard methods before use, wherever necessary.

Reagents/Solvents	Manufacturer
Ortho phenylenediamine	Chemi Loba
Hydrochloric acid	Universal chemicals and scientific ind.
Ammonia	Burgyon
Sodium hydroxide	CDH
Acetone	SD fine
Absolute alcohol	Bengal chemicals
Aniline	SD Fine
Potassium hydroxide	CDH
Aniline	SD Fine
Ethanol	CDH
Ammonium chloride	Sisco research lab
2- chloro benzoic acid	CDH
4- chloro benzoic acid	CDH

METHODS

Synthesis of 2AD {2-(1H-benzimidazole-2-yl)-N- phenyl aniline} Step-1(2-(2'-Chloro phenyl) 1H-benzimidazole)

o-Phenylene diamine (1.08g, 0.01 mole) and 2-chlorobenzoic acid (1.56g, 0.01 mole) both in stoichiometric proportion

were taken in ethanol as solvent in presence of NH₄Cl catalyst. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 80°C on hot plate. After the completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled and poured in the ice cold water. The granular solid was obtained. It was crystallized from the alcohol.

Step-2 {2-(1H-benzimidazole-2-yl)-N- phenyl aniline}

A mixture of 2-(2-chloro phenyl) benzimidazole (0.01)mole, substituted primary aromatic amine(0.01 mole) and KI (0.01mole) in 50ml of ethanol is heated under the reflux for 6 hrs. KOH (0.01mole in 50mL of water) was added with continuous stirring for 2hrs. Finally, the reaction mixture was left aside with room temperature and then poured in crushed ice. The solid product that precipitated is filtered off, recrystallized from ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccators.

Synthesis of 2BD (4-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-N-phenylaniline)

Step -1;2-(4-chlorophenyl)-1H-benzimidazole

o-Phenylene diamine (1.08g,0.01 mole) and 4-chlorobenzoic acid (1.56g,0.01 mole) both in stoichiometric proportion were taken in ethanol as solvent in presence of NH₄Cl a catalyst. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 80⁰C on hot plate. After the completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled and poured in the ice cold water. The granular solid was obtained. It was crystallized from the alcohol.

Step-2; (4-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-N-phenylaniline)

A mixture of 4-chloro methyl benzimidazole (0.01)mole, substituted primary aromatic amine(0.01 mole) and KI (0.01mole) in 50ml of ethanol is heated under the reflux for 6 hrs. KOH (0.01mole in 50mL of water) was added with continuous stirring for 2hrs. Finally the reaction mixture was left aside with room temperature and then poured in crushed ice. The solid product that precipitated is filtered off, recrystallized from ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccators.

METHOD OF PURIFICATION

The synthesized compounds were purified by using the following techniques.

Recrystallisation

After the synthesis of individual products in each synthetic step the products were purified by

Re crystallisation using appropriate solvents.

- Recrystallization of step 1 product using ethanol,
- Recrystallization of step II product using ethanol,

Thin layer chromatography (TLC)

The compounds synthesized were confirmed for its purity by TLC using suitable solvent system.

METHODS OF CHARACTERISATION:

The synthesized compounds were characterized by melting point, vibrational spectra (IR), NMR spectra and Mass spectra.

Melting point determination

The melting points were determined on Remi apparatus and were presented uncorrected.

IR spectra

IR spectra of the synthesized analogues were recorded using KBr pellets in the range of 4000-500 cm^{-1} on Jasco FTIR model 4100 type A, from vellore institute of technology, vellore.

NMR Spectra

^1H NMR spectra of the synthesized compounds were recorded using TMS (Tetra methyl silane) as internal standard and deuterated chloroform as solvent in Bruker Ultrashield Model 400 from Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore.

Mass Spectra

Mass spectra of the synthesized compounds were recorded by FAB⁺ ionization mode on JEOL. JMS 600 instrument in greens med lab, Thoraippakkam.

BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION

MTT assay

In vitro determinations of toxic effects of unknown compounds have been performed by counting viable cells after staining with a vital dye. Alternative methods used are measurement of radioisotope incorporation as a measure of DNA synthesis, counting by automated counters and others which rely on dyes and cellular activity. The MTT system is a means of measuring the activity of living cells via mitochondrial dehydrogenases. The MTT method is simple, accurate and yields reproducible results. The key component is (3-[4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]- 2, 5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) or MTT, is a water soluble tetrazolium salt yielding a yellowish solution when prepared in media or salt solutions lacking phenol red. Dissolved MTT is converted to an insoluble purple formazan by cleavage of the tetrazolium ring by mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzymes of viable cells. This water insoluble formazan can be solubilized using DMSO, acidified isopropanol or other solvents (Pure propanol

or ethanol). The resulting purple solution is spectrophotometrically measured. An increase or decrease in cell number results in a concomitant change in the amount of formazan formed, indicating the degree of cytotoxicity caused by the test material.(3.7)

Materials & Methods

1. MTT reagent (the solution is filtered through a 0.2 μm filter and stored at 2–8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for frequent use or frozen for extended periods)
2. DMSO
3. CO₂ incubator
4. Micro Plate reader
5. Inverted microscope
6. Refrigerated centrifuge

Preparation of test solutions

For MTT assay, serial two fold dilutions (3.125-100 μg) were prepared from this assay. Cell lines and culture medium MCF-7 cell line was procured from NCCS, stock cell was cultured in medium supplemented with 10% inactivated Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), penicillin (100 IU/ml), streptomycin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) in an humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ until confluent.

Source of reagents: DMEM, FBS, Pen strip, Trypsin procured from Himedia.

Procedure:

The monolayer cell culture was trypsinized and the cell count was adjusted to 1.0×10^5 cells/mL using respective media containing 10% FBS. To each well of the 96 well microtiter plate, 100 μL of the diluted cell suspension (1×10^4 cells/well) was added. After 24 h, when a

partial monolayer was formed, the supernatant was flicked off, washed the monolayer once with medium and 100 μ L of different concentrations of test samples were added on to the partial monolayer in microtiter plates. The plate was then incubated at 37°C for 24 h in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. After incubation the test solutions in the wells were discarded and 20 μ L of MTT (2 mg/mL of MTT in PBS) was added to each well. The plate was incubated for 4h at 37°C in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. The supernatant was removed and 100 μ L of DMSO was added and the plate was gently shaken to solubilize the formed formazan. The absorbance was measured using a microplate reader at a wavelength of 570 nm. The percentage of viability was calculated using the following formula, % of viability = Sample abs/Control abs x 100

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

2D QSAR MODEL

2D-QSAR models were generated to determine the effect of structural features thiadiazole as antiproliferative agents. The correlation matrix for nine descriptors and their IC₅₀ values used to generate models for equation 1. The linear regression method was used to perform the 2D-QSAR models by establishing the statistical linear correlation for nine descriptors taken as independent variables and pIC₅₀ as the dependent variable of the training data. The best model was selected based on statistical parameters such as observed squared correlation coefficient ($r^2 > 0.6$), which is a relative measure of the quality of fit. The cross validated leave one out squared correlation coefficient (q^2) should be high for predicting the goodness of the QSAR model, and the difference between q^2 and r^2 should not be more than 0.3. The standard error of estimate ($SEE < 0.3$) represents an absolute measure of prediction accuracy. In the above QSAR equations, r is the correlation coefficient of regression for the training set; r^2 is the square of the correlation coefficient of regression for the training set; q^2 is the square of LOO, the cross-validated correlation coefficient, RMSE is the root-mean-square error. The experimental pIC₅₀ values of the data set and their new predicted pIC₅₀ values by equation 1, 2, 3. Equations 1, 2 and 3 present five descriptors for each equation correlated with the biological activity (pIC₅₀) to indicate that these three predictive equations showed good statistical values for the training group with high r^2 values (equation 1, $r^2 = 0.9369$; equation 2, $r^2 = 0.9323$, equation 3, $r^2 = 0.9118$). To predict the ability of models as statistically significant by the cross-validated q^2 (equation 1, $q^2 = 0.8523$; equation 2, $q^2 = 0.8467$, equation 2, $q^2 = 0.7979$), the difference between r^2 and q^2 should not be more than 0.3, which is the essential condition to qualify a QSAR model as valid. From

the correlation, there is inverse relationship between parachor, AlogP, AATS2p, MATS2v, GATS1c, SpAD_Dzv descriptors and biological activity values. There is a direct relationship between molar volume, AATS8m, AATS1v, density, AATS4v, AATS1p, AATSC5i, MATS8s, CrippenMR descriptors and biological activity with different correlation coefficients.

TABLE 1: 95% CONFIDENCE OF EQUATION

VARIABLE	Coeff	std. coeff	co.Int.95%
Intercept	-7.0733	0.7386	
MATS8v	-1.5424	-0.2577	0.9666
SpMin4_bhi	2.5783	1.1239	0.4757

TABLE 2: THE REPORTS OF EQUATION**EQUATION 1**

	MATS8V	SpMin4_bhi	CIC1
MATS8v	1		
SpMin4_bhi	-0.805368807	1	
CIC1	-0.559624876	0.819734679	1

TABLE 3: THE REPORTS OF EQUATION 3**EQUATION 3**

	ATSC8V	SpMin4_bhi	CIC1
ATSC8V	1		
SpMin4_bhi	-0.271547882	1	
CIC1	-0.027427844	0.819734679	1

PARITY PLOT

The plot of the experimental pIC50 values versus their predictions of the training set and test set with 30% confidence interval parity plot (equation 1, equation 2, equation 3) are shown in Figures 3.8 , 3.9 and 4

Figure 1: Parity Plot of the pIC50 values with 95% confidence intervals for equation 1

Figure 2: Parity Plot of the pIC50 values with 95% confidence intervals for equation 2

Figure 3: Parity Plot of the pIC50 values with 95% confidence intervals

We get the relationship between model r2 and model q2 when they are plotted. Following figure 4 ,5 and 6 shows the relationship of equation 4.1,4.2 and 4.3.

FIGURE 4 : It shows the relationship of model r2 and q2 of equation 1.

FIGURE 5: It shows the relationship of model r2 and q2 of equation 2.

FIGURE 6: It shows the relationship of model r2 and q2 of equation 3.

IN SILICO SCREENING OF DESIGNED COMPOUNDS

The ADME properties of the designed compounds were evaluated using SWISS ADME software, and their results were tabulated. Toxicity of all the designed compounds was evaluated by using ProTox II software and the results were tabulated. The designed compounds are inactive for mutagenicity and cytotoxicity. Anticancer agents generally possess greater number of hydrogen bond acceptors. All the designed compounds have less than 5 hydrogen bond donors and 6-10 hydrogen bond acceptors. This obeys Lipinski rule of rule. The molecular weight of all the designed compounds was less than 500 daltons.

All our designed compounds showed log P value between 1- 5. It was found that lipophilicity plays a major role in determining where drugs are distributed within the body after adsorption and, as a consequence, how rapidly they are metabolized and excreted. In the biological system drug disposition depends on the ability to cross membranes, so there is a strong relationship with measures of lipophilicity. So, there is a strong lipophilic character of the molecule plays a major role in producing the antimicrobial effect. TPSA has been used as descriptor for characterizing absorption and passive transportation properties through biological membranes, allowing a good prediction of transport of candidate drugs in the intestines and through the blood-brain barrier. Compounds with TPSA values within the range 140 Å² have good intestinal absorption. TPSA (Total Polar Surface Area) of our designed compounds were found to be in the range of 88-140 Å². Therefore, it is expected that our compounds might possess good intestinal absorption.

DOCKING:

Docking is a method which predicts the preferred orientation of one molecule to a second when bound to each other to form a stable complex. Knowledge of the preferred orientation in turn may be used to predict the strength of association or binding affinity between two molecules using. In this study, Autodock Vina is used to perform docking studies. Docking studies were performed with the active site of Thyrosine kinase (PDB

ID: 2SRC). Protein was downloaded from RCSB protein data bank and used for docking analysis.. Compounds exhibited binding energies of -8.9\ -9.3\ -8.5\ - 9.3\ -9.3\ -6.5\ -9.2 kcal/mol, respectively. Results are shown in the table below.

TABLE 4 MOLECULAR DOCKING RESULTS OF NOVEL BENZIMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES AGAINST TYROSINE KINASE(2SRC) BY AUTODOCK VINA

COMPOUND	BINDING AFFINITY
2AD	-9.5
2BD	-9.3
2CD	-8.5
2DD	-9.3
2ED	-9.3
2FD	-6.5
2GD	-9.3
2HD	-9.2

2D and 3D diagrams of some structure are as follows; 2AD

2GD

2HD

2ID

The synthesized compounds were ascertained for their purity through R_f values and the melting points were checked and were presented uncorrected. Synthesised molecules were characterized by analytical and spectral studies.

MELTING POINT AND R_f VALUE DETERMINATION

Melting point of the synthesized pyrazoline substituted benzimidazole analogues were determined on Remi apparatus and were presented uncorrected. R_f values of the synthesized analogues were determined by thin layer chromatography.

Table: 5 Characteristic Melting points and R_f Values of the selected benzimidazole analogues

COMPOUND CODE	MELTING POINT($^{\circ}$ C)	R_f VALUE
2AD	280-282 $^{\circ}$ C	0.70
2BD	278-280 $^{\circ}$ C	0.72
2CD	274-278 $^{\circ}$ C	0.68
2DD	290-294 $^{\circ}$ C	0.64
2ED	280-282 $^{\circ}$ C	0.74

IR SPECTRAL ANALYSIS

IR spectra were recorded using KBr pellets in the range of 4000- 500 cm^{-1} on Jasco FTIR model 4100 type A to elucidate the structure of the compounds. The presence of characteristic peak of functional groups in the IR spectra of the synthesized benzimidazole analogues substantiates the formation of the designed compounds.

Table: 6**Characteristic IR peaks obtained for the selected benzimidazole analogues**

COMPOUND CODE	IR PEAKS (cm ⁻¹)
2AD	3183.51 (Ar-NH stretching), 2909.09 (Ar-C-H), 2817.69 (Ali C-H), 1738.51 (C-C stretching), 1622.38 (Ar C=N), 1483.96 (Ar C=C stretching) 1358.21 (C-N stretching tertiary amine)
2BD	3465.46(Ar-NH stretching), 2980.54 (Ar-C-H), 2366.52 (Ali C-H), 1670.34 (Ar C=N), 1498.52 (Ar C=C stretching), 747.281(C-Cl)

Schematic diagram represents IR SPECTRA of 2AD

NMR SPECTRAL ANALYSIS:

NMR (400 MHz) spectra were recorded on Bruker Ultrashield Model 400 MHz spectrometer using deuterated chloroform as solvent and TMS (Tetra methyl silane) as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ ppm).

The presence of characteristic peak of protons in δ ppm found in ¹H NMR spectra of selected benzimidazole analogues substantiates the formation of the designed compounds

TABLE:7

Atom number	Proton	δ ppm
1	1H, NH of benzimidazole)	7.956
6	CH	7.939
7	CH	7.934
9	CH	7.585
11	CH	3.301
12,13	CH, CH	7.568
14,15	CH, CH	7.563
16	NH	7.951
18	CH	7.568
19,20	CH,CH	7.580
21,22	CH, CH	7.585

Schematic diagram represents H NMR SPECTRA of 2AD

¹³C NMR SPECTRA

Schematic diagram represents C- NMR SPECTRA of 2AD

MASS SPECTRAL ANALYSIS

TABLE :8

Sample code	Base peak (m/z)	Molecular ion peak (m/z)
2AD	211.14	363.21

SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM REPRESENTS MASS SPECTRA (VE) OF 2AD

BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION:

Cytotoxicity studies on human breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) was conducted at the Green meds lab, Thoraipakkam, Chennai. The effect of compounds on the proliferative capacity of the breast cancer cells (MCF-7) was determined using MTT [3-(4, 5 dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2, 5- diphenyltetrazolium bromide] assay. The synthesized compounds which showed good Glide score was evaluated for the activity at different concentrations from 3.125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The compound showed an IC₅₀ value of **132.80 μg .**

The results of the MTT assay are shown in Table 13.

Table:9

CONCENTRATION	% OF VIABILITY
3.125	95.5399061
6.25	85.56338028

12.5	74.53051643
25	69.83568075
50	60.68075117
100	54.342723

Schematic diagram represents MTT ASSAY OF 2AD

MTT assay – MCF7 cell line

2-AD

DISCUSSION

A quantitative analysis of the structure activity relationship (QSAR) was performed on a data set of 30 compounds of benzimidazole derivatives as anticancer agents. The 2D-QSAR model for a series was established using multiple linear regression (MLR) methods that yielded a regression model with good predictive power. The predictability of the proposed

models was demonstrated by various methods, including cross-validation, external evaluation, the root-mean-square error (RMSE) and parity plot. All of these results showed the good statistical parameters of models to predict the activity for developing new compounds as anticancer agents. The developed 2D-QSAR model expressed by equation 1 was used to predict the biological activity (pIC₅₀) of newly designed benzimidazole derivatives as anticancer agents against tyrosine Kinase. From the results, 10 designed compounds can act as potential anticancer agents against tyrosine Kinase. The results were acceptable giving significance to model equation descriptors supporting QSAR studies.

In silico studies were performed on all the designed compounds and the compounds with good results and less toxicity are selected for docking studies. Based on the docking results 5 compounds are selected for synthesis. Preliminary characterization of all the synthesized compounds was conducted. Spectral characterization of 2AD was done by IR, NMR and Mass spectroscopy. Among the synthesized compounds one with the highest dock score was selected for anticancer activity study on breast cancer cell line (MCF-7.) The compound 2AD studied for cytotoxicity studies against breast cancer cell line by MTT assay method showed highest activity with an IC₅₀ value of t **132.80 µg**. Hence, further studies can be conducted using this compound by increasing its concentration and also by increasing the incubation period.

CONCLUSION

The current research work was focused on design and synthesis of novel aniline substituted Benzimidazole analogues as anticancer agents. A quantitative analysis of the structure activity relationship (QSAR) was performed on a data set of 30 compounds of benzimidazole derivatives as anticancer agents. The 2D-QSAR model for a series was established using multiple linear regression (MLR) methods that yielded a regression model with good predictive power. The developed 2D-QSAR model expressed by equation 1 was used to predict the biological activity (pIC₅₀) of newly designed benzimidazole derivatives as anticancer agents. Computer aided drug design is required to design new compounds before synthesis, thus reducing the cost by filtering the compounds. Preliminary *In Silico* molecular modeling was carried out with the help of available computational softwares. Among the proposed analogues, those obeying Lipinski's rule of five and drug likeness profiles and with good dock score and less toxicity were selected for the wet lab synthesis. Purity of the compounds thus synthesized was ascertained by consistency in melting point and R_f value. The compounds were characterized using IR, NMR and Mass spectral studies. In vitro pharmacological screening of the synthesized analogues for anticancer activity study on breast cancer cell line (MCF-7.) was performed by MTT assay. The compound 2AD showed good cytotoxicity on the breast cancer cell line compared to standard with an IC₅₀ value of t **132.80 µg**. The results of our study are promising and encouraging. The synthesized novel molecules showed significant anticancer activity as compared to standard drugs. We sincerely hope that these studies will stimulate further research in this direction and will result in the development of better therapeutic agents with improved efficacy in near future. Hence we consider these derivatives as future leads for anticancer drug discovery.

Reference:

1. SerefDemirayak1 and Leyla Yurtta, Synthesis and anticancer activity of some 1,2,3-trisubstituted pyrazinobenzimidazole derivatives, *J Enzyme Inhib Med Chem*, 2014 Dec;29(6):811-22,Epub 2014 Jan 2
2. SumitTahlan, Design, synthesis and biological profile of heterocyclic benzimidazole analogues as prospective antimicrobial and antiproliferative agents, *BMC Chemistry*, Article number: 50 (2019), Published: 03 April 2019
3. Rose Dawn Bharath, recent development of target based benzimidazoles as a potential anticancer activities, *Biological Chemistry*,published 2 Jan 2002.
4. Pu Xiang, Novel Benzothiazole, Benzimidazole and Benzoxazole Derivatives as Potential Antitumor Agents: Synthesis and Preliminary *in Vitro* Biological Evaluation, *Molecules*. 2012 Jan; 17(1): 873–883.Published online 2012 Jan 17.
5. Kantharaju kamanna, synthesis and pharmacological profile of benzimidzole, submitted; November 9th,2018 reviewed; February 15th, 2019 published : August 13th,2019
6. ALI EL-SHEKEIL ,ABEER OMER OBEID , Anticancer activity studies of some cyclic benzimidazole derivatives, *European Journal of Chemistry* 2012, 3(3), 356-358, Published: 30 Sep 2012 | Issue Date: September 2012
7. Ravinesh Mishra , DESIGN AND SYNTHESIS OF BENZIMIDAZOLES CONTAINING SUBSTITUTED OXADIAZOLE, THIADIAZOLE AND TRIAZOLO THIADIAZINES AS A SOURCE OF NEW ANTICANCER AGENTS , *Arabian Journal of Chemistry* Volume 12, Issue 8, December 2019, Pages 3202-3224.
8. Hanan MM . refaat , SYNTHESIS AND ANTICANCER ACTIVITY OF SOME NOVEL 2- SUBSTITUTED BENZIMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES ,*European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*Volume 45, Issue 7, July 2010, Pages 2949-2956

9. Mohammed Abed, synthesis, characterization and biological screening of some 2 substituted benzimidazoles as a potential anticancer agents, published Jan 1 2016. Journal of Chemistry Research.
10. Ali el Shekeil, Anticancer activity studies of some cyclic benzimidazole derivatives,
European Journal of Chemistry 2012, 3(3), 356-358, Published: 30 Sep 2012 | Issue
Date: September 2012
11. Amar Djemoui, A step-by-step synthesis of triazole-benzimidazole-chalcone hybrids: Anticancer activity in human cells⁺ *Journal of Molecular Structure*, Volume 1204, 15 March 2020, 127487
12. Kamaldeep Paul, Synthesis of new conjugated coumarin-benzimidazole hybrids and their anticancer activity, *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*, 2013 Jun 15;23(12):3667-72. Epub 2013 Jan 4.
13. Vaishali S Shinde, Synthesis of benzimidazole nucleosides and their anticancer activity , *Carbohydrate Research* Volume 498, December 2020, 10817
14. Jae Eun cheong, Synthesis and anticancer activity of novel water soluble benzimidazole carbamates, *Eur J Med Chem*, 2018 Jan 20;144:372-385, Epub 2017 Dec 14
15. Asmaa A Mad El din , Benzimidazole – Schiff bases and their complexes: synthesis, anticancer activity and molecular modeling as Aurora kinase inhibitor , Published by De Gruyter September 6, 2018.